

A new precipitation-conductometric titration technique for heavy metal ions in water

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Abstract : A new precipitation-conductometric titration technique has been developed for the determination of Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Hg^I , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} in coloured solutions. Solution of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC) has been used as a titrating reagent.

Keywords : Conductometric titration, heavy metal ions, sodium diethyldithiocarbamate.

In continuation to our previous work¹, analytical applications of dithiocarbamates (DDCs), precipitation-conductometric titrations of heavy metal ions in water are described in present work.

Experimental

Apparatus and procedure : Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (GBC902, Australia), conductivity meter (ElicoM180) and spectrophotometer (ElicoCL124, India) were used. Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC) and disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) (LR) from CDH, New Delhi were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade.

Solutions of metal salts (0.1, 0.3 M) and NaDDC (0.1, 0.2 M) were made in distilled water. All other solutions were made as usual². The samples of spinach, Pepsi (Varun Beverages Ltd., Mathura) and Apple Juice (Parle Agro Ltd., Ghaziabad) were collected in May 2005, from Aligarh.

Aliquot of 0.5 ml of nickel chloride solution (0.3 M) was taken in a 25 ml standard volumetric flask and made up to 25 ml with distilled water. The conductometric titration was performed into a 50 ml beaker by adding 0.2 M NaDDC solution from the burette. Similarly the solutions of Ca^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mg^{2+} nitrates, $CoCl_2$, $NiCl_2$, $MnSO_4$ and $(NH_4)_2Fe(SO_4)_2$ were titrated.

Determination of Hg^{II} in various samples : A solution of mercuric nitrate (1 ml of 0.3 M) was added to a beaker containing 19 ml distilled water and 5 ml tap water or 5 ml of

pepsi or 5 ml of 20% apple juice. The admixture was stirred and titrated with 0.2 M of NaDDC solution. The tap water alone was also titrated as above and no end point was obtained i.e. the conductivity increases with increasing volume of the titrant. Aqueous solution of pepsin (20%) did not consume the titrant. In order to determine Hg^{II} content of spinach, green spinach (100 g) was crushed, mixed with 25 ml of distilled water and filtered to obtain the green extract. The total volume was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. An admixture containing 19 ml distilled water, 5 ml of spinach extract and 1 ml of 0.3 M mercuric nitrate was titrated as above.

Composition of metal dithiocarbamate complexes : Solution of nickel chloride (1 ml of 0.1 M) and NaDDC (2 ml of 0.1 M) was taken in a conical flask and mixed thoroughly. Precipitate obtained was washed with distilled water, filtered and washed 3-4 times and transferred into a conical flask with 5 ml of distilled water, dissolved in minimum amount of conc. HNO_3 and final volume was made up to 100 ml. The metal ion concentration was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The concentration of diethyldithiocarbamate was determined by the following procedure. The precipitate was transferred in a conical flask with distilled water, shaken thoroughly to make uniform suspension and the total volume was made up to 100 ml. An aliquot of 10 ml of copper sulphate (0.2%) and 5 ml of citric acid (25%) were taken in a 100 ml conical flask. The mixture was made alkaline with ammonia, excess ammonia was boiled off and then 15 ml of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (4%) were added to it. A known volume of the suspen-

sion was added to this reaction mixture and contents were mixed thoroughly in order to get a clear solution. The reaction mixture was cooled at room temperature (35 °C), transferred into a separatory funnel and the yellow product was extracted in 10 ml butylacetate. The absorbance was measured at 430 nm against the reagent blank.

Table 1. Results of precipitation-conductometric titration

[NaDDC] 0.2 M, volume of titrant 2.0 ml

Titrant		Titrant	
[Metal ion]	Metal	Volume	Metal
0.3 M	taken	consumed	found
	(mg)	(ml)	(mg)
Pb(NO ₃) ₂	123	6.0	124
Zn(NO ₃) ₂ 6H ₂ O	36.5	6.0	36.7
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ H ₂ O	121	5.2	105
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ 4H ₂ O	67.0	5.8	65.0
CoCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	36.0	6.0	35.0
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ 3H ₂ O	38.0	5.6	36.0
(NH ₄) ₂ Fe(SO ₄) ₂ 6H ₂ O	34.0	5.2	29.0
NiCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	35.2	6.0	34.8
Fe(NO ₃) ₃ 9H ₂ O	34.5	6.8	38.0
Hg ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ 3H ₂ O	120	6.4	128

Results and discussion

The solubility of metal dithiocarbamates is more in ethanol than that in water. Therefore, water has been found to be a suitable medium for metal ion versus dithiocarbamate precipitation conductometric titration. The following three types of different characteristics have been obtained: (1) in case of titration of Hg^I, Hg^{II}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} against NaDDC the conductivity decreases in beginning but increases after the end point, (2) in case of Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} the conductivity remains almost constant in the early stages of titration and after the end point is passed however, the excess of the added salt causes a sharp increase in the conductivity and (3) in case of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} the conductivity increases continuously with the incremental concentration of NaDDC so the end point of titration can not be determined. Table 1 shows that ten metal ions, which follow the aforesaid titrations (1) and (2) can be determined successfully.

Table 2 shows that the ratio of concentration (composition) of Pb^{II} or Cd^{II} or Zn^{II} or Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} to diethyldithiocarbamate is 1 : 2. Results of Jobs method are in good agreement with those of chemical analysis. However, the reverse titration i.e. NaDDC against metal salt solution did not yield good results because of no inflexion was observed to indicate the end point. It may be due to the formation of metal hydroxide along with metal diethyldithiocarbamate, i.e. pH value of 0.1 M aqueous solution of NaDDC is 9.8 so metal hydroxides are also formed.

Table 2. Composition of metal diethyldithiocarbamates

Compd	Jobs method		Chemical analysis			
	Metal	Diethyldithiocarbamate	Metal		DDC	
			Calcd (ppm)	Found (ppm)	Calcd (µg)	Found (µg)
Pb ^{II} diethyl-dithiocarbamate	1	2	6.0	4.80	59.2	44.0
Cd ^{II} diethyl-dithiocarbamate	1	1.9	1.0	0.87	58.0	39.0
Zn ^{II} diethyl-dithiocarbamate	1	2	0.98	0.70	42.0	39.0
Ni ^{II} diethyl-dithiocarbamate	1	2	5.0	4.50	59.0	31.0
Cu ^{II} diethyl-dithiocarbamate	1	2	5.0	4.60	60.0	46.0

Conclusion :

Precipitation-conductometric titration technique can be successfully applied for the determination of heavy metal ions such as Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Hg^I, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} using sodium diethyldithiocarbamate as a titrant. The technique is useful for monitoring of the heavy metal ions in distilled water, river water, tap water, and coloured solutions such as apple juice, beer, pepsi, wastewater, wine etc.

References

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